

RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AS A MEASURE TO PREVENT THE DEPLETION OF THE OZONE LAYER

Scientific supervisor: A.O.Imamova., student M.N.Bobonazarova., D.O.Sanokulova
Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179223

Introduction: We all know that since the 20th century, the level of air and environmental pollution is increasing as a result of the development of industrial technologies and climate change. The air contamination compromises the ozone layer and consequences in the formation of the Ozone Hole, resulting in greater incoming radiation to earth it potentially disrupts the biological life and processes. Ozone layer depletion resulted from rapid industrialization, high consumption of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and halons, and global warming have further worsened the problem towards more destruction. The industrial exhaust gases and automobile fuel gases produced as a result of urbanization create a greenhouse effect and this is the main factor leading to depletion of the ozone layer which causes damaging by excess ultraviolet lights. Reducing the fossil fuel contribution to the global energy system, and in particular doing so with renewable energy sources, is a great challenge for the world community.

Key words: renewable energy sources, bioenergy, solar energy, wind power, hydropower

Main part: Among the renewable energy sources, hydropower is presently the most important source for electrical power generation. It also provides grid stability and reliability, as well as balancing support to intermittent renewable energy, such as wind and solar power. The global contribution of hydropower, in a 40-year perspective, is estimated to be around double that of today. Bioenergy is a versatile energy source that can be used to produce electricity, heat and fuels. Forestry and agricultural residues, along with organic waste, are expected to be the main future biomass energy options. By 2050, bioenergy is expected to contribute about 20% of global energy supply and 10% of global electricity production. Bioenergy will grow in importance, and forestry and agricultural residues, along with organic waste, are expected to be the main future biomass energy options. The added agricultural production of biofuels may not have a net positive climate effect and will have to compete with food production for land and water. The global population of 9-10 billion people expected in 2050 will need food with an energy content of about 10,000 TWh per year (2,500 kcal/person/day), which is several times more energy than fossil fuels provide today.

Solar energy using direct sunlight is potentially the most powerful renewable energy source for electricity and heat. The technologies are developing rapidly, and in 2050, solar energy is expected to contribute up to 6% of the total global energy supply

and 6% of the global electricity production. The main solar power constraints are high costs and its intermittency. However, while global energy prices are rising, the costs for solar energy are decreasing. Concentrating solar power (CSP) has the potential to provide significant amounts of base-load power, but is not expected to be viable in areas without much direct sunlight. Solar energy technologies are developing rapidly and may become major global energy providers in the next 40 years. Solar's base exceeds that of all other renewable alternatives, but the breakthrough has so far been limited by high costs and the intermittent nature of sunlight. CSP with integrated thermal storage has the potential to provide significant amounts of power at base load, but will only be feasible in areas with high direct solar input, i.e. in or near desert regions. Exporting electricity from these areas requires long-range, high-capacity continental power grids. Small-scale solar energy systems such as photovoltaics and heating panels are expected to become increasingly important at the local level. Extensive research and development needs still remain to develop viable large-scale solar energy solutions.

Wind power is a rapidly increasing source of renewable electricity generation, with the main constraint for its development being related to its intermittency. A balancing power source is therefore needed. Today, balancing power comes mainly from fossil fuels. In order to reduce fossil fuel use, a combination of hydropower and wind power constitutes an excellent combination. A future development of large-scale energy storage facilities may allow for greater long-term expansion of wind power. In 2008, wind power provided 0.2% of the global energy supply. It is a rapidly increasing source of renewable electricity generation, with the main constraint for its development being related to its intermittency. A balancing power source is therefore needed. Today, balancing power comes mainly from fossil fuels. In order to reduce fossil fuel use, a combination of hydropower and wind power constitutes an excellent combination. With the estimated hydropower development and the main aim to minimize the use of fossil fuels, the 2050 share of wind power is expected to be around 3–4% of the global energy supply and 12–15% of global electricity production. A future development of large-scale energy storage facilities may allow for greater long-term expansion of wind power.

Hydropower plays a key role, among the renewable energy sources, with a unique capacity to quickly respond to fluctuating electricity demands. It has large development possibilities in different parts of the world, but there are a number of essential social and environmental obstacles and constraints to its development. Most of the potential for hydropower development is found in developing countries, while the EU, for example, has already tapped most of the readily available resources.

Conclusion: The ozone layer acts as a natural filter, absorbing most of the sun's ultraviolet rays coming towards the earth's atmosphere. we can prevent its depletion by minimizing fossil fuels that produce greenhouse gases and using renewable energy sources.

References:

1. Fredga, K., K. Danell, H. Frank, D. Hedberg, and S. Kullander. 2008. *Bioenergy, opportunities and constraints*. Energy Committee Report, June 2008, Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences.
2. Pihl, E. 2009. *Concentrating solar power*. Energy Committee Report, April 2009, Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences.
3. Crutzen PJ, Mosier AR, Smith KA, Winiwarter W. N₂O release from agro-biofuel production negates global warming reduction by replacing fossil fuels. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*. 2008;8:389–395. doi: 10.5194/acp-8-389-2008. [[CrossRef](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
4. Destouni, G., and A. Darracq. 2009. Nutrient cycling and N₂O emissions in a changing climate: The subsurface water system role. *Environmental Research Letters* 4:035008 (7 pp). doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/4/3/035008.
5. Energy Committee at the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences. 2008. Statements on solar energy. Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, 10 November 2008.